

PROFICIENCY IN THE USE OF MODAL AUXILIARIES

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study is to assess the proficiency level of modal auxiliary verbs utilization of the Grade 9 students from schools A and B. The researcher used the descriptive design since this aims to assess the difference in the proficiency of the respondents in the use of modal auxiliary verbs when the respondents are grouped according to sex and school of origin. Specifically, the researcher aimed to assess the proficiency of the respondents in the proper use of modal auxiliary verbs; most frequent error committed by the respondents; and the difference of the proficiency of the respondents when they were grouped according to sex and school of origin. This research used causal-comparative method with the aid of questionnaire as the main tool for data gathering. The researcher employed the percentage formula in determining the profile of the respondents and the mean was used to determine the respondents' proficiency level and the most frequent error committed. In determining the significant difference between the proficiency level of the respondents as to their sex and school of origin, the t-Test was used. After a thorough and careful analysis and interpretation of the gathered data, the researcher arrived at the following findings: 1. The most frequent error committed by the respondents was on the proper use of the modal auxiliary verb "could"; 2. The proficiency level of the respondents in the use of modal auxiliary verbs is poor; 3. There is a significant difference in the proficiency of the respondents when grouped according to sex. Results showed that females' proficiency level is higher than the males.' However, there is no significant difference between the proficiency of the respondents when it comes to school of origin; and 4. In terms of sex, the female respondents showed a higher preference for using modal verbs.

Keywords: *modal, auxiliary, verbs, frequency, proficiency, index*

INTRODUCTION

English has always been one of the official languages in the Philippines. It is the language of commerce and law, as well as the primary medium of instruction in education. The English language is well entrenched in Philippine formal education. Therefore, schools should try to develop the English language proficiency of Filipino students. The usefulness of English in such settings have been intensified by globalization in its various manifestations. According to Regala (2017), Filipino educators will have to be exceptionally creative in finding ways to ensure that English becomes a positive resource in the education of Filipinos.

On the other hand, teachers have to be given the chance to enhance their knowledge and literacy in the English language in order to contribute to the much deserved change in the Philippine Educational System.

According to Education First English Proficiency Index 2018, the Philippines was ranked 14th of the 88 countries and regions with high proficiency of 61.84% and positioned 2nd in Asia. For the last three years, the Philippines was ranked 13th, (2016); 15th, (2017); and 14th, (2018). Females have higher proficiency of 62.57% compared to males' 60.85%. Results showed that English proficiency improved overall; the societies that speak English are more open, less hierarchical, and fairer to women; English and innovation go hand in hand; women speak English better than men; adults in their twenties speak the best English; managers have a better grasp of English than executives or staff.

The impetus for this study grew out of three considerations. The first is the importance of modality in language use. This has attracted the attention of linguists who are concerned with and have taken pains to address the issue of linguistic expressions of modality. The linguistic study of modality is still full of vitality. The reason behind it may be largely due to the linguists' profound awareness that the function of language is first and foremost communication, Chenfeng (1989). The second consideration concerns the claims of many grammarians and linguists that English modal system is a difficult area both descriptively and pedagogically. The third consideration comes from the present researcher's observation of Grade 9 students' modal performance.

The modal auxiliaries of English verb system is one of the most troublesome grammatical structures yet very important part of studies both in spoken and written aspects. Past research has shown that learners of English seem to have difficulty in using modal verbs appropriately and that they frequently overuse or under-represent certain modal meanings or forms (DeCarrico, 1986; Hinkel, 1995 as cited by Yang, 2018). That is why, mastering modal auxiliary verbs is needed so that students would be able to use English language accurately. In case of social interaction, students are believed to have problems in using modals that might lead to difficulty in conveying meanings they wish to

express and that indeed might be the reason why they do not recognize that they sometimes sound unpleasant (Thornbury, 1999 as cited by Mukundan, 2011).

On the other hand, problems in writing performance on modal auxiliary verbs are known among many secondary students in School A. Based from the result of their diagnostic test conducted on 5th of June 2018, from which modal auxiliary verbs are part of, it was found out that students have difficulties recognizing the accurate uses of modal auxiliary verbs.

Therefore, the researcher was prompted to determine the proficiency level in using modal auxiliary verbs of the Grade 9 students of School A and School B, School Year 2018 – 2019. Further, the researcher believes that the result of the study will help students know better the importance and functions of the modal auxiliary verbs, and to learn from commonly misused expressions to avoid ambiguity, confusion, misunderstanding and embarrassment through teaching them with the enhancement program which emphasizes the correct usage of modal auxiliaries.

Studies on modal auxiliary verbs became widespread even before. It is in this reason that modals have been proved to be one of the most troublesome grammatical structures in English (Khojasteh, Shokpour and Torabiardakani, 2015). It is enormously complicated because the same modals sometimes are used to express different functions.

In his *Difficulty in Learning Modal Verbs*, Sawasdithep (2014) states that the process of teaching or learning English especially as a second language is quite challenging due to the complicated nature of modal verbs used. Various forms of communications from asking permissions to responsibility usually have varying forms of expression. Hence, modal verbs are important in facilitating an efficient and understandable communication pattern in the society and therefore, they form significant aspect in human language. It would be hard to persuasively tell somebody something or present science project without the use of modal verbs. Modal verbs enhance the texts to be much precise and clear in its meaning. A communication pattern without proper structure is deemed to fail, thus the necessity of having good knowledge on the grammar involved for efficient communication. Modals are generally complex entities, and if possible way to simplify them was found, learners could experience fewer problems when learning English.

A study conducted by Khojasteh and Reinders (2013) regarding the use of modal auxiliaries, still of the Malaysian learners, revealed that students were uncertain about which modals to use in their sentences, and this could easily be seen in the inaccuracy of modals at the syntactic and specifically semantic levels.

Modality is extremely important in academic written discourse as it conveys the writer's attitude both to the propositions he/she makes and to the readers. The ability to use modality appropriately contributes significantly to pragmatic aspect in English writing (Hyland, 1994; Myers, 1989 as cited by Yang, 2018) and may reflect an advanced level of

both linguistic and pragmatic proficiency in the written mode (Chen, 2010 as cited by Yang, 2018).

Research Questions

The main purpose of the study is to assess the proficiency level of modal auxiliary verbs utilization of the Grade 9 students from school A and B for the Academic Year 2018-2019. Specifically, it is directed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of sex?
 2. What is the proficiency of the respondents in the use of the modal auxiliaries when grouped according to:
 - 2.1. sex;
 - 2.2. school of origin?
 3. What is the most frequent error committed by the respondents when grouped according to:
 - 3.1. sex;
 - 3.2. school of origin?
 4. Is there a significant difference of the proficiency of the respondents when grouped according to:
 - 4.1. sex
 - 4.2. school of origin?
 5. What is the frequency of modal used by the respondents when they are grouped according to sex?
 6. What enrichment program may be proposed to enhance the students' competence in the utilization of modal auxiliaries?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Environment

The locale of the study were Jagna High School and BIT IC High School.

Jagna High School is located at Bunga Mar, Jagna, Bohol, approximately 2.5 kilometers from the Poblacion (town proper) and 60 kilometers from the city of Tagbilaran. The said institution was established in 2012, and has housed an enrollment of 556 junior high school students and 207 senior high school students.

BIT IC High School- Jagna Campus is located at Poblacion, Jagna, Bohol whose population for school year, 2018-2019 reached to 655, of whom 357 are males and 298 females.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Grade 9 Jagna High School and BIT IC High School

students enrolled in the school year 2018-2019. Jagna High School had 31 males and 36 females, while BIT IC High School had 25 males and 39 females. The total number of respondents was 131 of whom 56 are males, and 75 are females.

Research Instrument

The researcher made use of a questionnaire to gather the necessary data needed for the study. The said questionnaire is divided into two (2) parts. The first part is all about the demographic profile of the respondents. The second contains the modal auxiliary verb test questions designed by Sevastopoulos, (2017).

On demographic profile. This component determines the respondents' sex and school of origin.

On questionnaire in Modal auxiliary verb test. The test has a total of fifty-four (54)-item multiple choice questions to ascertain the proficiency of the students in the utilization of modal auxiliary verbs namely: (1) can, (2) could, (3) may, (4) might, (5) must, (6) shall, (7) should, (8) will, and (9) would. Each type is tested in 6 items. This 54-item test makes use of a 5-point scale criterion which ranges from high to very poor. A mean of 6.00 was defined as high, while a mean of 0.00 was defined as very poor.

The result of the computed mean for the respondents' proficiency level is interpreted using the following scale:

Scale	Descriptive Value	Interpretation
4.9 – 6.00	High	Respondents' competency is high.
3.7– 4.8	Above Average	Respondents' competency is above average.
2.5 – 3.6	Average	Respondents' competency is average.
1.3 – 2.4	Poor	Respondents' competency is poor.
0.00 – 1.2	Very Poor	Respondents' competency is very poor.

The result of the computed mean for the most frequent error among the modals was interpreted using the following scale:

Scale	Descriptive Value	Interpretation
4.9 – 6.00	Most Frequent	Very low performance level
3.7– 4.8	More Frequent	Low performance level
2.5 – 3.6	Frequent	Satisfactory performance level

1.3 – 2.4	Less Frequent	Very satisfactory performance level
0.00 – 1.2	Least frequent	High performance level

Research Procedure

Gathering of Data. A thorough preparation was made before the investigation was conducted. First, a letter of request to conduct the study was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor of the District of Jagna and to the respective School Principal of Jagna High School as the locale of the study.

Another letter of request to conduct the study was sent to the Director of BIT IC Jagna Campus and to the Principal. Once the approval was granted, the test and the questionnaire were personally conducted and distributed to the students. The researcher personally administered the test to the respondents. The said test and questionnaire determined the respondents' sex, school of origin, and measured their knowledge in the proper utilization of modal auxiliary verbs through encircling the letter of the correct answer and by constructing sentences using the modal auxiliaries. The respondents were given sixty (60) minutes to answer. The collected data were then tallied and statistically treated.

Statistical Treatment

1. To determine the profile of the respondents, the researchers used percentage formula:

$$P = F/N \times 100$$

Where:

P = Percentage

F = Frequency

N = No. of cases

2. To determine the proficiency level of the respondents, the researcher used the:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

Where:

\bar{x} = Mean

\sum = Summation

x_i = i^{th} individual observation

n = total number of observations

3.

To determine the most frequent error committed by the respondents in terms of the nine (9) modal auxiliary verbs, the researcher used the Average formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

Where: \bar{x} = Mean
 \sum = Summation
 x_i = i^{th} individual observation
 n = total number of observations

4. In determining the significant difference of the proficiency level of the respondents as to their sex and school of origin, the t-test for independent samples was used.

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{SS_1 + SS_2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}\right)\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)}}$$

Where:

t = the computed t-test
 \bar{x}_1 = mean percentage score of the first variable
 \bar{x}_2 = mean percentage score of the second variable
 SS_1 = sum of the square of variances of the first variable
 SS_2 = sum of the square of variances of the second variable
 N_1 = number of students of the first variable
 N_2 = number of students of the second variable

Scope and Limitation

The proficiency of students in the use of modal auxiliaries was the main variable of the study. The proficiency has limited from very poor to high. The sex is also deemed important to be included in this study so there would be basis for remediation and enhancement to which sex needs to be helped in this competence.

The limitation of the study was focused to Grade 9 students only, and not the whole population of each campus. It was the Grade 9 students who have the lesson on modal auxiliary verbs.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

SCHOOL	School A (Number/Percent)	School B (Number/ Percentage)	TOTAL (%)
MALE	31(23.66%)	25(19.08%)	56 (42.75%)
FEMALE	36(27.48%)	39(29.77%)	75 (57.25%)
TOTAL	67(51.15%)	64(48.85%)	131 (100%)

Table 2. Respondents' Proficiency in the Use of Modal Auxiliary Verbs in Terms of School of Origin

Modal Auxiliary Verbs	School A			School B		
	Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank	Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
Can	2.97	Average	1	3.0	Average	1
Shall	2.73	Average	2	2.86	Average	2
Must	2.41	Poor	3	2.66	Average	3
Should	2.10	Poor	4	2.19	Poor	4
May	1.61	Poor	5	1.73	Poor	5
Will	1.6	Poor	6	1.44	Poor	7
Might	1.24	Poor	8	1.59	Poor	6
Would	1.42	Poor	7	1.34	Poor	8
Could	1.03	Very Poor	9	0.92	Very Poor	9
Grand Mean	1.90	Poor		1.97	Poor	

Table 3. Respondents' Proficiency in the Use of Modal Auxiliary Verbs in Terms of Sex

Modal Auxiliary Verbs	Male			Female		
	Mean	Descriptive value	Rank	Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
Can	3.05	Average	1	2.93	Average	1
Shall	2.73	Average	2	2.84	Average	2
Must	2.64	Average	3	2.45	Average	3
Should	1.91	Poor	4	2.32	Poor	4
May	1.41	Poor	6	1.87	Poor	5
Will	1.55	Poor	5	1.49	Poor	7.5
Might	1.30	Poor	7	1.49	Poor	7.5
Would	1.21	Poor	8	1.51	Poor	6
Could	0.88	Very Poor	9	1.05	Very Poor	9
Grand Mean	1.85	Poor		1.99	Poor	

Table 4. Most Frequent Error Committed by the Respondents when Grouped According to Sex

	Male			Female		
	Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank	Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
Modal Auxiliary Verbs						
Could	5.13	Most Frequent	1	4.95	Most Frequent	1
Would	4.79	More Frequent	2	4.49	More Frequent	4
Might	4.7	More Frequent	3	4.51	More Frequent	2.5
May	4.59	More Frequent	4	4.13	More Frequent	5
Will	4.45	More Frequent	5	4.51	More Frequent	2.5
Should	4.09	More Frequent	6	3.68	More Frequent	6
Must	3.36	Frequent	7	3.55	Frequent	7
Shall	3.26	Frequent	8	3.16	Frequent	8
Can	2.94	Frequent	9	3.07	Frequent	9
Grand Mean	4.15	More Frequent		4.01	More Frequent	

Table 5. Mean Difference of the Proficiency Level of the Respondents in Terms of Sex and School Of Origin

Respondents	Mean Score	Tabular t-value	Computed t-value	Level of Significance	Decision	Interpretation
Male	16.34	1.978	2.199	0.05	Reject null hypothesis	Significant
Female	18.11					
JHS	17.01	1.978	0.844	0.05	Accept null hypothesis	Not significant
BIT HS	17.70					

Table 6. Frequency of Modals Used by the Respondents when Grouped according to Sex

Modal Auxiliary Verbs	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Ranking	Frequency	Ranking
Can	16	2	70	1
Shall	3	4	0	9
Must	0	8.5	2	5
Should	3	4	17	3
May	1	7	1	7
Will	36	1	39	2
Might	0	8.5	1	7
Would	3	4	9	4
Could	2	6	1	7
Total	64		140	

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents from School A and School B campuses. School A has 67 test takers or 51.15% of whom 31 or 23.66% are males and 36 or 27.48 are females, while School B has 64 or 48.85% of whom 25 or 19.08% are males and 39 or 29.77% are females. This means there are 56 or 42.75% male and 75 or 57.25% female respondents.

Presented in Table 2 is School A and B respondents' proficiency in the use of modal auxiliary verbs. Result shows that modal verb "can" obtained the mean of 2.97 and 3.0 respectively, ranked as the highest correctly used verb whose descriptive value is "average". Likewise, modal verb "shall" whose means are 2.73 and 2.86 is within the "average" range. Modal verb "must" whose means are 2.41 and 2.66 is "poor" for School A, but "average" for School B. The modal verbs "should", "may", "will", "might", and "would" belong to "poor" for both schools. On the other hand, the modal verb "could" with means of 1.03 and 0.92 was in the lowest rank with a descriptive value of "very poor".

The grand means of 1.90 and 1.97 have a corresponding descriptive value of "poor". This means that School A and B respondents' proficiency did not meet the desired standard. The result appeared to be almost identical with the study conducted by Al-Hessa (2014) who found out that students' proficiency level in the utilization of modal auxiliary verbs is very poor. It implies that the students had a serious problem when it came to choosing the most appropriate modal verb to be used in oral or written discourses.

Presented in Table 3 is the male and female respondents' proficiency in the use of modal auxiliaries. Based on the result, the modal verb "can" obtained the highest mean of 3.05 and 2.93 whose descriptive value is "average" for both male and female

respondents. Next in rank are “shall” and “must” whose descriptive value is within the “average” range. Both sexes’ proficiency for “should”, “may”, “will”, “might”, and “would” is to “poor”. On the other hand, the modal verb “could” with a mean of 0.88 and 1.05 is in the lowest rank with a descriptive value of “very poor”.

Over all, the grand means of 1.85 and 1.99 have a descriptive value equivalent to “poor”. The result is in consonance with the study conducted by Khojasteh and Reinders (2013) which revealed that Malaysian students were uncertain about which modals to use in their sentences, and this could easily be detected in the inaccuracy of modals at the syntactic and specifically semantic levels.

Scale	Descriptive Value	Interpretation
4.9 – 6.00	Most Frequent	Very low performance level
3.7– 4.8	More Frequent	Low performance level
2.5 – 3.6	Frequent	Satisfactory performance level
1.3 – 2.4	Less Frequent	Very satisfactory performance level
0.00 – 1.2	Least frequent	High performance level

Table 4 presents the most frequent error committed by the respondents from both sexes wherein “could” is the first in rank. This generated the highest mean of 5.13 and 4.95 respectively based on the degree of errors as shown in the answers of the male and female students from both schools. The frequency of error is described as “most frequent” which indicates that students’ performance level is very low. For instance in the item, “You ___ look into alternative financial sources for your home.” The choices are could, would, should and shall. The respondents have real confusion when it comes to determining which of these modals is the most appropriate to use.

Meanwhile, the male students incur the lowest mean of 2.94 compared to females’ 3.07 in the usage of “can.” Both correspond to the descriptive value of “more frequent” which means that students’ performance level in the proper usage of the said modal is deemed satisfactory. In the same manner, the respondents’ competence in the correct use of “shall” and “must” is in the frequent range.

The male respondents’ grand mean of 4.15 and the females’ 4.01 fall in the “more frequent” range which reveals the students’ low performance level.

This result is in consonance with the study of Vethamani, Manaf and Akbari (2008) which showed that most Malaysian ESL learners were able to use appropriate verb forms on their own, but when a modal was present, meaning became indefinite in some sentences and the verb form tended to be incorrect.

Table 5 presents the mean difference between the modal proficiency level of the male and female respondents. The null hypothesis is rejected because the computed t-value of 2.199 is greater than the tabular t-value of 1.978 where the level of significance is set at 0.05 whose degree of freedom is 10.

Result also shows the mean difference between the respondents' modal proficiency in terms of the school of origin. Since the computed t-value of 0.844 is less than the tabular t-value of 1.978 where the level of significance is set at 0.05 with a degree of freedom of 10, the null hypothesis is confirmed.

Thus, there is a significant difference between the respondents' proficiency level in terms of sex. The result corresponds with the study of Al- Hessa (2014) which revealed that there is a significant difference between males' and females' performance level in the proper utilization of modal verbs since females obtained a higher mean score.

Nevertheless, there is no significant difference between the respondents' proficiency level when it comes to school of origin. The result jibes with Khojasteh and Reinders' study (2013) which traced the same pattern where students were uncertain about which modals to use in their sentences.

Table 6 presents the frequency of modal verbs used by the respondents when they are grouped according to sex. The modal verb "can" ranked first in the frequency count. This was used 70 times by the female respondents. Meanwhile the modal verb "will" ranked first in the male respondents' output. This occurred 36 times. The respondents' preference in terms of the use of "can" and "will" varies. The female respondents preferred to use "can", while the male respondents opted to use "will".

None from the male respondents used "must" and "might", while "shall" is missing in the female respondents' write-up.

The over-all result indicates that the frequency of modal verbs in the male respondents' output is lesser compared to their female counterparts'. Except "shall", the rest of the modal verbs appeared 140 times in the female respondents' essays indicating that the female respondents' preference in the usage of modal verbs is high.

Conclusions

1. Evidently, there are differences in the frequency of use of the nine verb phrase structures in which modals can occur in language utilization among the respondents (Khojasteh, 2011).
2. Respondents are not really exposed to other verb structures, particularly structures with passive, progressive, and perfect aspects. A single modal has several meanings and the modal's meaning has both a logical and a practical element.
3. Though there have been a large bulk of studies examining the general development sequence in L1 acquisition, not many studies have concentrated exclusively on the English modal auxiliary system.
4. Since students are obviously learning the English modal auxiliaries over time, their mastery grows across levels and their use of modal forms progresses from less stable to relatively more so. However, despite the progress students have made, the modal

auxiliary system remains a difficult area. This has been confirmed in the claims made by many researchers and linguists.

5. Knowing how weak or strong our students are in terms of any grammatical structure specifically modal auxiliary verbs, EFL teachers are expected to be proficient enough even outside the classroom walls where they have to use conventional English to ensure that students fully grasp the modal verbs' various meanings.

Recommendations

1. Students should be aware of the functional appropriateness of modal auxiliary verbs to avoid confusion, misunderstanding and ambiguity.
 2. All the nine central modals must be introduced and repetitively taught to enhance students' understanding. Introducing modals according to function is an appropriate method of introduction. Drilling is one that could be used so that students can see the usage and be able to use the modals well.
 3. Teachers must consider teaching modals in a structured way to enhance understanding.
 4. Teaching students forms and functions of linguistic items must be continued and reinforced so that students will get sufficient exercises that will enable them to practice and understand the usage of modals and their functions.
 5. There should be a collaboration between authors and curriculum planners to ensure consistency between course contents and course competencies.
 6. The respondents' failure to reach the desired proficiency is the top concern which needs to be addressed. Though there is just slight difference of proficiency when the respondents are grouped according to sex, still enforcement and reinforcement of learning modal auxiliaries are helpful and necessary to both sexes since their proficiency level is poor.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, strict adherence to ethical principles was paramount. Prior to participation, all respondents were provided with comprehensive information about the study's objectives, procedures, and potential risks, ensuring their informed consent. It was emphasized that participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents retained the freedom to withdraw from the study at any stage without penalty or repercussion. To uphold confidentiality and protect the anonymity of participants, identifying information was carefully safeguarded and omitted from any reporting or analysis. Furthermore, measures were in place to safeguard the well-being of respondents throughout the study process. There was a commitment to transparency and integrity, with the assurance that no conflict of interest influenced the conduct or outcomes of the research. Rigorous efforts were made to prevent plagiarism, and all sources were appropriately credited.

Additionally, every effort was made to ensure impartiality in the interpretation of findings, mitigating any potential bias. The results of this study are intended solely for research purposes and will be used to contribute to the existing body of knowledge in the field, with the utmost respect for ethical standards and academic integrity.

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